

COMPUTER AIDED DRUG DEVELOPMENT (CADD) PROCESS AND SCREENING: HIGH THROUGHPUT SCREENING (HTS)

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ABSTRACT

Computer aided drug development (CADD) comprises of a broad range of theoretical and computational approaches, CADD method have a major role in modern drug discovery, design and development that plays a major part in clinical use and clinical trials .it also highlights the current trends and methods used in development of novel methods i.e. computer aided repurposing and emerging concepts and technologies in molecular modeling and chemo informatics. In this once the drug molecule is identified/selected it is processed for development. In which different parameters of lead compound are assessed on basis of vitro assay (experimental analysis), vivo model (animal studies) and silicon approach (software based). From the last decade incremental developments in R&D processes, the selection of tools for optimizing the functionality and viability has become the important factor in early drug development and is said to be the key for development of effective therapeutic agents. Drug design is important part of drug development, identification of active components in natural products gives lead compounds for development into drug. The current process of High Throughput Screening (HTS) through wet chemistry or in silicon is reviewed. The development of drug through protein engineering is used for antibody drug conjugates to improve specificity. HTS has the capacity to profile thousands of chemical concentrations response formats with reduce rate of false positive and false negative, therefore from last decade it used for compound libraries screening. Titration based quantitative screening is used for toxicology.

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INTRODUCTION

The Significance of discovery screening and structure optimization studies

Computer-Aided Drug Design and Development

Computer-aided drug design (CADD) has been credited to the modern patterns in compound characterization in drug discovery following its inception in 1981. It represents advancement when compared to HTS as it requires minimal compound design or prior knowledge, but can yield multiple hit compounds among which promising candidates have been elected. The typical role of CADD in drug discovery is to screen out large compound libraries into smaller clusters of predicted active compounds (Figure 1), enabling optimization of lead compounds by improving the biological properties (like affinity and ADMET) and building chemo types from a nucleating site by combining fragments with optimized function. Clustering has been applied as a means to select representatives from screening libraries. Screening hits include molecules that specifically bind to the target in addition to a greater number of nonspecific compounds requiring a triaging process to filter these out. Thus, such a large library that contains a number of possible hits is further downsized and clustered into series.

Computational chemistry algorithms have been developed to group hits based on structural similarity, which is necessary to ensure that compounds are adequately sorted over a broad spectrum of chemical classes. Thus, selection of hits would be based on chemical cluster, potency, and factors such as ligand efficiency (which gives an idea of how well a compound binds for its size).

Figure 1: Screening of Drug-Like Compounds into Activity Criteria.

The increasing application of diverse computerized methods in drug discovery has enabled a better handling of data associated with a large number of compounds screened against the target molecules or proteins for leads. Computational tools help to define and elaborate the strength of interaction between ligands and targets, and have been instrumental in the identification of lead molecules from databases. Nevertheless, the lack of specificity leads to low hit rate for HTS, which could limit its applicability and efficiency in screening large compound libraries. CADD is a more targeted approach to the generation of “hits” when compared with traditional HTS. It enables the elucidation of the molecular basis of therapeutic activity and possible derivatives, and those variables that could be applied or improved for generating an optimal drug compound, thus leading to prioritization of the actives without requiring extensive development and validation prior to use, as in the case of assay HTS. The CADD approach has played a vital role in the search and optimization of potential lead compounds with a considerable gain in time and cost. It has been applied during various stages in drug discovery: target identification, validation, molecular design, and interactions of drug candidates with targets of interest.

CADD can be structure or ligand based. Structure-based CADD seeks the knowledge of the target protein structure in the determination of interaction levels of all compounds being examined. Ligand-based CADD relies on the chemical similarity criteria, and the predictive, quantitative structure–activity relationship (QSAR) models that it creates from the molecules to determine the known active and inactive. QSAR modeling enables understanding of the influence of structural factors on biological activity, using the models and the understanding to construct compounds with improved and optimal biological profiles. Other methods for quantitative description of structural change are comparative molecular field analysis and GRID.

Structure-based CADD is a preferred choice for soluble proteins that could be crystallized, while ligand-based CADD is better suited for compounds with high binding affinity to the target, devoid of off-target effects, and that could be designed with minimal free energy, favorable drug metabolism, and pharmacokinetic/ADMET properties. In general, CADD is better suited for occasions where sparse structural information is available. This is usually the case for membrane protein targets.

Drug Development Strategies

Computer-aided drug design uses computational approaches to discover, develop, and analyze drugs and similar biologically active molecules. The ligand-based computer-aided drug discovery (LB-CADD) approach involves the analysis of ligands known to interact with a target of interest. These methods use a set of reference structures collected from compounds known to interact with the target of interest and analyze their 2D or 3D structures. The basic objective of these methods is to predict the nature and strength of binding of given molecule a target. Abinitio quantum chemistry methods, or density functional theory, are frequently used to deliver optimized parameters for the molecular mechanics calculations to predict the conformation of the small molecule and to model conformational changes in the biological target that may occur when the small molecule binds to it. The data also provide an estimate of the electronic properties (electrostatic potential, polarizability, etc.) of the drug candidate that will influence binding affinity. CADD methods can surge the probabilities of recognizing compounds with desirable characteristics, hustle up the hit-to-lead development, and expand the odds of getting a compound over the many obstacles of preclinical testing.

Figure 2: Characteristic features of CADD.

Design of Experiment in pharmaceutical development

DOE and one factor at a time experiments

Traditionally, process development experimentation focuses on changing one factor at a time. This approach is based on varying one independent factor while keeping other independent factors constant. This approach intrinsically cannot detect interactions between factors. The major advantage of using design of experiments (DOE) to develop and optimize manufacturing processes and control is that DOE takes into account all input variables simultaneously, systematically, and efficiently. Each single input variable and multi-variables interaction can be evaluated and their effect(s) on each response variables can be identified.

STEP 1: DEFINE THE OBJECTIVE

A research scientist in a pharmaceutical company decided to screen some of the input factors for initial assessments for their potential effects on the product (Edible water Blob) yield of suitable quality.

STEP 2: DEFINE THE EXPERIMENTAL DOMAIN

Based on prior knowledge of the process and in-house data, the researcher selected the following variables to investigate by conducting the minimum number of experiments. The factors and ranges used in the study are shown in Table 1 below. All factors are numerical values. For each factor, the study investigates only the variation in the effect of changing from the lower to the upper value. Table 1 lists the range of each input variable in their actual values and in coded values (numbers in parentheses). In coded variables, the lower value of each factor is set to -1 and the higher value of each factor is set to +1.

STEP 3: SELECT THE EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

SPC for MS Excel provides simplified statistical procedures under DOE covering the full factorial designs, the fractional factorial designs, and the Plackett-Burman Designs.

The software defines the factors as the following:

- Factor A = Binder
- Factor B = Granulation Water
- Factor C = Granulation Time
- Factor D = Spheronization Speed
- Factor E = Spheronization Time

STEP 4: DEVELOP THE STATISTICAL MODEL

The purpose of initial factorial screening is to assess the effect of each input variable on the response variable. The initial assumption was that the result (% Yield) of each trial will consist of linear combination of the input variables. A reasonable model for the analysis of this experiment is proposed as a linear relationship between the response variable and the input variables:

$$Y_{ijklmn} = \mu + B_i + W_j + GT_k + SS_l + ST_m + E_{(ijklm)n}$$

Where:

Y_{ijklmn} = Response variable (yield) to be analyzed

μ = Overall mean

B_i = Effect of i^{th} % binder

W_j = Effect of j^{th} % water

GT_k = Effect of k^{th} granulation time

SS_l = Effect of l^{th} spheronization speed

ST_m = Effect of m^{th} spheronization time

$E_{(ijklm)n}$ = within error, NID ($0, \sigma^2$)

STEP 5: RUN THE DESIGN AND PERFORM THE STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The experimental runs are completed. Statistical analysis and ANOVA of the experimental data were performed using the fractional factorial experimental design module provided by SPC for MS Excel. The output of the statistical analysis includes the design table and the ANOVA table.

STEP 6: DEVELOP CONCLUSIONS

The results indicate that speed and length of the spheronizer (SS and ST) process within the studied range had negative effect on the yield of desired quality pellets while the % binder and % granulation water showed positive effect on the yield of proper pellets quality. The negative effects of SS and ST can be understood by the fact that high SS and/or long ST cause the pellets to stick together making triplicates and quadruplicates, which itself makes the pellets to grow larger than the desired sizes.

This study has determined which of the five factors had a significant impact on the yield. Confirmation runs would be required to ensure that the results are valid.

High-Throughput Screening

Definition

High throughput screening (HTS) is the use of automated equipment to rapidly test thousands to millions of samples for biological activity at the model organism, cellular, pathway, or molecular level. In its most common form, HTS is an experimental process in which 10^3 – 10^6 small molecule compounds of known structure are screened in parallel. Other substances, such as chemical mixtures, natural product extracts, oligonucleotides, and antibodies, may also be screened. Because HTS typically aims to screen 100 000 or more samples per day, relatively simple and automation-compatible assay designs, robotic-assisted sample handling, and automated data processing are critical. HTS is commonly used in pharmaceutical and biotechnology companies to identify compounds (called hits) with pharmacological or biological activity. These are used as starting points for medicinal chemical optimization during pharmacological probe or drug discovery and development. Typically, HTS assays are performed in microtiter plates in 96-, 384-, or 1536-well formats while traditional HTS usually tests each compound in a compound library at a single concentration, most commonly 10 μ M.

Quantitative high throughput screening (qHTS) is a method of testing compounds at multiple concentrations using an HTS platform. The concentration response curves are generated for each compound tested immediately after the screen is performed. Recently, qHTS has become popular in toxicology because it more fully characterizes the biological effects of chemicals and decreases the rates of false positives and false negatives.

Development & Modification of Bioactivity

High-Throughput Screening

HTS, as the name indicates, is a drug discovery process that enables a biochemical or cellular event to be reproducibly and rapidly tested against chemical entities many hundreds of thousands of times. HTS utilizes robotics (**Figure 3**), liquid handlers, data processing, considerable software, and sensitive detection systems. The objective of HTS is to rapidly identify active compounds that modulate a particular target, pathway, or biochemical/cellular event. The output from a HTS campaign provides the basis upon which drug design and elaboration are used to generate lead compounds with appropriate physicochemical properties for therapeutic indications.

Figure-3: Example of robotics used in high-throughput screening laboratory.

HTS approaches are now being utilized more and more to facilitate ADMET/DMPK (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, toxicity/drug metabolism and pharmacokinetics) activities, as the major pharmaceutical companies have adopted frontloading of these stages of the drug discovery process. Academic researchers are also increasingly making use of HTS facilities to identify probes used in chemical biology, helping to facilitate identification of new potential drug targets, and also to increase their knowledge about known targets

High Throughput Screening in Drug Discovery

High throughput screening (HTS) is one of the leading technological breakthroughs in drug discovery. The pharmaceutical industry strictly depends on HTS for generating hits from the explosive library of the compound database. The stepwise screening strategy tends to eliminate both compounds that fail the standard criteria and the probability of errors generated. Robotic and automation technology permits handling of an enormously large number of compounds. Robotic liquid handlers are tailored technologies for micro pipetting at blistering speeds, well suited to over a million screening assays conducted within 1–3 months. Since initial screens always need validation and optimizations for any drug discovery approach, the relevance or usefulness of HTS is not directly determined. In general, due to project complexity, a number of procedures and techniques confirm function and delivery of the right drug compound that is not directly attributable to HTS. An important part of cell-based HTS is high content screening, which has drawn interest because of its multiplexing ability and the efficiency in enabling detection of functional cell characteristics. High throughput experimental technologies have stimulated increasing incorporation of the systems' point of view in cellular and molecular biology, promoting the study cells as systems.

The Significance of Discovery Screening and Structure Optimization Studies

HTS has been instrumental to the empirical approach to drug discovery, which is based on trial and error but not on any prior known biological properties or mechanism of action. It has been dedicated to early drug discovery processes, but is now increasingly being integrated to downstream processes of lead optimization, encouraging scientists and engineers to streamline workflows with reduced timelines. The changing drug discovery program that incorporates parallel programs (which is shifting from the earlier sequential process of the past) allows much of the information generated to be utilized concurrently, and thus increases the number of compounds generated through robotic systems. The multidimensional workflow and use of low-volume assays underlie its cost effectiveness. Increased miniaturization, through micro- or nanochip-based approaches and on-bead screening, has helped to expand its capabilities. Solid-support-on-bead screening has reduced reactions to nanoscale levels, making it easier to process large datasets within a short period of time. Thus, high throughput screening is no longer a concern.

Larger databases provide a greater variety of options and more insight into possible leads during the critical stages of the discovery process. The timely access of information allows a more managed and distribution system. The statistical computations and algorithms are proven standards that permit better organization of HTS data for high performance.

Development of the Molecular Libraries Initiative, the Molecular Libraries and the Screening Center Network, and eventually the Production Center Network was part of the National Institutes of Health Roadmap program strategy to advance chemical biology. This led to the setting up of translational- and chemical-screening programs at academic screening centers in many US universities. All contributed to generating diverse chemical libraries and the development of novel chemistries based on HTS. These tools are indispensable in advancing understanding of complex biology for target and disease pathway identification and are well-validated potential medical therapies.

Molecular Cell Biology

HTS

HTS is another approach for identifying potential drug candidates. The success of HTS is dependent on the identification of meaningful assay systems. One example is the development of peptide substrates for the measurement of IgA1 protease activity in a 386-well microplate assay system (Choudary *et al.*, 2013). Microplate formats now range from 4 wells/plate to 1536 wells/plate; most HTS procedures use 96 well plates, 386 well plates, or 1536 well plates. The use of higher density plates greatly increases screening output; use of a 96-well plate allows 10 000 compounds to be screened per day, 40 000 compounds per day with a 384-well microplate, and 200 000 compounds per day with a 1536-well microplate.

Other solid phase assay formats can also be used, such as microfluidic chips for cell-based screening systems (Young, 2013). The process of HTS is costly and can be labor-intensive depending on the extent to which robotics are used in the process. A relatively new approach to HTS is fragment-based screening (Schulz and Hubbard, 2009) which involves a smaller library of small molecules which are evaluated for the binding to a target. Fragments which bind are then assembled into larger compounds which are then evaluated for binding to a target.

Combinatorial Screening

Combinatorial or high throughput screening (HTS) is the process for rapid automated assessment of single or multiple properties of a large number of samples, most often fabricated as a combinatorial “library.” Combinatorial materials science combines a small number of starting chemical reagents in all combinations defined by a given reaction scheme, with the combinations of process conditions to yield a large number of well-defined products. The resulting library of products is often further tested against some set of performance parameters, followed by the high throughput analysis of properties of the fabricated materials. The early successes of combinatorial chemistry and high throughput chemical analysis in the pharmaceutical industry have been followed with the discovery of a wide variety of important materials in chemistry and materials science. These materials range from catalysts, polymers, and zeolites to luminescent and magneto resistive compounds, to agricultural materials and high-temperature superconductors, dielectric, ferroelectric, and structural materials, and to many others. Parallel synthesis and rapid screening of new materials for useful properties opened up the exploration of multidimensional chemical composition and process parameter space at a previously unavailable level of detail. This added greatly to the chance of finding a global reaction optimum. Also, this approach allowed statistically well-founded empirical rules to be derived for optimization strategies (Schlögl 1998). Further, it provided significant savings in time and cost per sample. A classic example of a comprehensive screening of materials space is the work of Mittasch, who from 1900 to 1909 performed 6.5–10\$ screening experiments of 2.5–10\$ catalyst candidates to find a catalyst for industrial ammonia synthesis (Ertl 1990). In 1970, Hanak demonstrated a “multiple-sample concept,” when he performed the parallel synthesis of materials by using gradient sputtering techniques to find new superconducting materials (Hanak 1970). The work by Xiang *et al.* on superconductors published in 1995 (Xiang *et al.* 1995) initiated an avalanche of advances in numerous areas of combinatorial materials science and HTS. This article will outline recent developments of HTS tools of combinatorial libraries of materials and methods to handle data from these instruments.

Current Concept of HTS In drug discovery, it was estimated that the number of molecules that could theoretically be made with structures and molecular weight attractive for screening for pharmaceutical activity is 10^{10} (Hann *et al.* 1999). This number is 10^8 times larger than the number of molecules available from commercial sources or in-house collections and 5×10^4 times larger than the CAS database. In organic chemistry, it was estimated that 10^8 potentially stable organic structures are possible with up to 30 atoms of hydrogen, carbon, oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur elements (Bohacek *et al.* 1996). In materials science, about 3–10\$ binaries, 7–10% ternaries, 1–10\$ quaternaries, and 6–10\$# decanaries were shown to be possible from 75 useful and stable elements in the periodic table, excluding stoichiometric and structural diversity and different orders (Maier 1999). Traditional approaches, when synthetic testing and characterization experiments are performed on a single sample at a time, will never be able to deal with this extensive materials space. In contrast, combinatorial materials science and HTS tackles this enormous diversity in a rational fashion (Schlögl 1998), when a large number of components is synthesized, tested against single or multiple performance parameters, and screened in parallel. Intrinsic properties of synthesized materials libraries are further evaluated. An additional testing step may include exposure of the materials library to a set of performance parameters such as temperature, electromagnetic field, mechanical stress, vapors, aggressive solvents, etc., that potentially may alter the materials properties. The effects of these testing conditions are determined in the in situ or post-testing screening with the goal of identifying leads—the library components with desirable properties that exceed a predefined statistically relevant threshold. Each stage of the combinatorial discovery cycle incorporates numerous innovations from different disciplines. These advances make possible automated preparation of libraries and handling picoliter-sized samples, rapid testing of materials against a variety of factors of interest, noncontact and nondestructive screening of resulting compounds, and efficient analysis, interpretation and management of large amounts of data. Depending on the scope of the work, any stage of the cycle may constitute a serious bottleneck in the development of a successful materials discovery program. An important aspect of library presentation to the HTS tools is the feasibility of high-precision handling of small-scale samples at all stages of the combinatorial cycle. A variety of automated instruments is available for the preparation, synthesis, screening, and storing of materials. These are typically designed around a multiwell format first adopted in the drug discovery industry

Data Handling

HTS operations typically generate massive amounts of data. Data handling and management are the key issues in executing the high performance operation of HTS. The large amount of data increases the need for effective data analysis and statistical methods to ensure the integrity of the data and to identify the trends and relationships in the data. Advanced mathematical and statistical chemo metric techniques (see *On-line Measurement*) are used in HTS to determine, often by indirect means, the properties of substances that otherwise would be very difficult to measure directly. In HTS, chemo metrics has been successfully applied for pattern recognition, lead identification and optimization, and other applications.

The pattern recognition goal is to find similarities and differences between chemical samples, based on measurements made on the samples. In HTS, pattern recognition techniques serve as the powerful visualization tool. They can reveal correlated patterns in large data sets, determine the structural relationship among HTS hits, and can significantly reduce data dimensionality to make it more manageable in the database. Methods of pattern recognition include principal components analysis (PCA), hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA), soft independent modeling of class analogies (SIMCA), neural networks, and some others (Beebe *et al.* 1998, Otto 1999).

Two typical approaches of pattern recognition analysis of HTS data are illustrated in Fig. 4 using data from a 48-element library of organic coatings as an example. Optical spectra of an array of 48 coatings that are shown in Fig. 4(a) indicate the variation of several measured properties of coatings. This variation is induced by variable performance and composition and deposition conditions. Each spectrum provided information about several parameters of a coating. Application of PCA automatically separated spectral contributions associated with different properties of the 48 coatings by providing a lower dimensional graphical representation that described a majority of the variation in a data set. KNM analysis for the determination of the similarity of coating elements in the array based on their measured properties.

Figure 4: Multivariate analysis of spectral variables of combinatorically synthesized material. (a) Optical spectra of 48 coatings. (b) Scores plot of the first three principal components (PCs) that accounts for > 95% variance captured by PCA. (c) KNM analysis for the determination of the similarity of coating elements in the array based on their measured properties.

Because it reduces the dimensions required to visualize the data, PCA is a powerful method for examining multidimensional data sets for expected or unexpected clusters, including the presence of outliers (Beebe *et al.* 1998). Figure 4(b) depicts a scores plot of the first three principal components which accounted for more than 95% variance captured by PCA. This plot shows several clusters associated with different spectral features. Also, upon performing PCA on the spectra, loading for respective principal components typically reveal the separate contributions of different effects on coatings.

Organizing a set of materials into clusters is often used in assessing the diversity of these materials by compositional or performance properties and in developing structure–property relationship models. The K-nearest neighbor (KNN) analysis, a specific type of HCA, is an example of determination of the similarity of coating elements in the array based on their measured properties. In the KNN analysis, links are made between nearest neighbors of adjoining clusters. With KNN, the predicted class of an unknown sample is assigned as the class of the samples nearest to it in multidimensional space. A measure that accounts for the different scales of variables and their correlations, is the Mahalanobis distance D^2 calculated by:

$$(3) D_{ij}^2 = (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)^T \mathbf{C}^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)$$

Where \mathbf{C} is the covariance matrix, \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j are column vectors for objects i and j , respectively, and T is the transpose operator. Scaling of data is not needed if the Mahalanobis distance is used. Results of the KNN cluster analysis are shown in Fig. 4(c). Clusters here are the groups of coatings that are related by compositional, deposition, or performance properties.

Multivariate calibration approaches permit selective quantitation of several analytes of interest in complex combinatorial libraries using low-resolution instruments, when overlapping responses from different species preclude the use of univariate analysis. Quantitative analysis is often performed using linear and nonlinear multivariate calibration methods such as partial least-squares, locally weighted regression, neural networks, and others. An example application of the multivariate calibration approaches is the implementation of an array of acoustic-wave sensors coated with diverse chemically sensitive films (Potyrailo *et al.* 1999) for analysis of volatile components in combinatorial reactions. Upon exposure of the array to samples with different amounts of analytes, the time dependent signal changes of each sensor were related to concentrations of analytes.

Selective quantitation of two analytes in complex mixtures was achieved by means of locally weighted regression analysis of the dynamic data, as shown in Fig. 5(a). This method is especially useful for modeling of nonlinear systems such as those used in the employed sensors (Potyrai et al. 1999). Overall advantages of the nonlinear methods are in their applicability for analysis of structurally heterogeneous data sets. These methods reduce the problems encountered using linear methods, when the underlying relationships involve nonlinearities, thresholds and interactions, all of which considerably impede linear additive modeling approaches. Using this sensor array, analysis of volatiles was accomplished on a much shorter time scale than using gas chromatography. Data presented in Fig. 5(b) demonstrate that maximum sensor response from one of the components of interest in the mixture was observed 10 s after exposure of the sensor to the volatile sample.

Figure 5: Application of chemical sensor arrays for the selective detection of multiple volatile components in combinatorial mixtures.(a) Locally weighted regression correlation plot for analyte vapors.(b) Representative dynamics response of the sensor array (channel 1) to increasing concentration of analyte vapors. Insert:response to solvent(865 g) and analyte(875 g).

Large amounts of data produced by HTS require new approaches for data manipulation. To reduce the amount of data from high-resolution instruments, different signal-compression methods can be applied. One such technique is wavelet analysis that has been used to compress data without appreciable degradation. Data compression is achieved by performing a wavelet transform on a 2-D or a 3-D signal (e.g., spectrum, image, etc) and selecting only the wavelet coefficients that contain the most relevant information. A representative example of a wavelet-transformed spectrum is shown in Fig. 6 along with the original Raman spectrum of a material of interest. Depending on the application needs, different scales of wavelet coefficients can be removed in the compressed signal. Although data compression is one of the most important applications of wavelets, this technique can be also applied to extract the relevant components from data for pattern recognition, classification, and multivariate calibration purposes. In addition, wavelet analysis is capable of revealing aspects of data that other signal analysis techniques miss: aspects such as trends, breakdown points, discontinuities in higher derivatives, and self-similarity (Misiti et al. 1997).

Information-rich output from the HTS advances the development of new appropriate database technologies. The major functions of a typical database include inventory and management of starting components and process conditions, handling heterogeneous HTS data, identification of leads, interfacing to library preparation robots, integration of inventory data with identified leads, and interfacing with other databases.

Figure 6: Example of the wavelet analysis of 2-D data. (a) Raman spectrum of an industrial polymer. (b) Representation of Raman spectrum in a wavelet domain.

Measuring Biological Responses with Automated Microscopy Meeting the Demand of High-Throughput Screening with Transfluo

High-throughput screening assays need to be predictive of the pharmacology of a test compound on its target, simple and easy to perform, robust, and automatable. The arresting GFP translocation assay has been shown to meet all of these requirements. First, it has been used successfully to determine the pharmacology of known agonists and antagonists for several GPCRs. Next, the Transfluo assay is performed easily because it involves a few, basic steps (Fig. 7). In contrast to other high-content screening assays, which require primary and secondary antibody incubations and washes after cell fixation, no wash steps are necessary with Transfluo. In addition, all steps in the assay are automated easily by liquid-handling robotics such as MultiDrops and MiniTraks, and detection of assay results has been validated on multiple, automated fluorescent imaging platforms (Oakley *et al.*, 2006). Furthermore, the assay is very reproducible and gives excellent screening statistics, including Z prime values above 0.5, ensuring an optimal screening assay window.

High Throughput Screening with Biofabrication Platforms

Figure 7: Transfluo screening protocol steps with associated liquid handling robotics.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

HTS started as a simple, fast, and cheap solution to perform the screening of large libraries with thousands of small molecules, making the drug discovery process easier. With the maturation of the technology, new limitations have been found and new solutions have been developed in order to make these screening techniques more reliable. Several bio-printing techniques have been used to dispense a wide range of materials with high accuracy, aiding significantly the results obtained in HTS assays. Due to the advantages of HTS methods, these have been adopted in several research fields such as stem cell research and biomaterials development. In order to screen a large number of conditions simultaneously *in vivo*, new implantable HTS platforms have also been developed.

Despite the numerous different approaches developed over the last years, it is still not possible to fully simulate the *in vivo* microenvironment *in vitro*, making it difficult to ensure the success of the hits normally identified with *in vitro* screenings. 3D models are gaining robustness and might aid in the better understanding of the *in vivo* microenvironment. Despite the complexity that can be achieved with 3D *in vitro* models, it is still impossible to fully replicate animal models and ultimately the human physiology. Integration of different technological platforms could be a solution in the near future to add complexity where needed and achieve an improved mimicry of human physiology. In this respect, integration of HTS techniques with microfluidic, sensing, and actuating platforms is expected to generate devices where it would be possible to react to certain sensed conditions and study dynamically the efficacy of new possible treatments. Translating these approaches to clinically relevant 3D models is of key importance and will require significant advances in imaging and data analysis. Future developments in HTS should address these limitations, while solutions that allow the screening of *in vitro* and *in vivo* on the same platform might help in a further understanding of these factors.

ABBREVIATIONS

HTS = High Throughput Screening

CADD = Computer Aided Drug Design

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